

THE EFFECTS OF CONTROL FACTORS ON THE ACCURACY OF PRETENDER COST ESTIMATING IN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Cost estimating is influenced by many factors ranging from those within the control and those beyond the control of the project team referred to as idiosyncratic factors. The study investigated through a field survey the perception of construction professionals on the influence of control factors affecting cost estimating in North Eastern geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Nineteen control factors were drawn from relevant literature and subjected to experts' scrutiny. The Relative Importance Index (RII) of these factors revealed that the topmost factors in the input control, output control and Behaviour control categories are the project scope definition (RII = 75.30), estimators experience (RII = 77.69) and expected accuracy (RII = 76.54) respectively. The study further revealed that the extremely important factors with RII of over 70% are the estimator's experience, expected accuracy, project scope definition, level of team integration, cost planning, effective communication, estimating methodology, historical data of similar contract, quality of the cost data, adequacy of resources for cost estimating, owners requirement clarity, completeness of design, benchmarking and experience in similar contract.

KEYWORDS: control factors, cost estimating, relative index, Nigeria

Introduction

The quality of early estimates is crucial to the feasibility analysis and budget allocation decision for public projects (Kim *et al.*, 2008a; Kim *et al.*, 2008b; Sonmez and Ontepeli, 2009 and Feng *et al.*, 2010). Overestimated cost could result in misjudgement for the feasibility of a project or loss of a contract to competitors. On the other hand, the contractor could incur significant losses from underestimated cost. Typically estimation of project efforts needs to be made at various stages of a project (Liu and Zhu, 2007). At the conceptual stage, a ballpark figure is needed to ascertain whether the feasibility of the project should be investigated. According to Akintoye (2000), Morison (2004) and Liu and Zhu (2007), most estimation techniques have inherent errors resulting from the estimating process and external factors still have significant influence on the accuracy of the estimation.

An accurate estimate is essential to ensure that projects are allocated sufficient budget so that functional requirements are met.

Accurate prediction of construction cost depends upon quite a number of factors (Enshassi *et al.*, 2007a). These factors has been identified by extant literature including those related to government regulation, plan changes, quality of the contractor, management team, project deadlines, project information, bidding situations, project characteristics, experience on similar type of project, the estimating process and the experience of the estimator (Shash and Al-Khadhi, 1992; Lowe and Skitmore, 1994; Chua *et al.*, 1999; Enshassi *et al.*, 2007a; Enshassi *et al.*, 2007b; Odusami and Onukwube 2008 and An *et al.*, 2010)

Factors Influencing Cost Estimating

Factors influencing construction cost estimation range from those that are within the control of the project team to those beyond the control of the project team referred to as idiosyncratic factors. The organizational control theory identifies three modes of controls that can be directed at achieving the behaviour necessary to secure desired performance (Liu and Zhu, 2007). These are the input control, behaviour control and the output control factors. Liu and Zhu (2007) categorised different factors influencing cost estimating into nine namely; project information, team experience, cost information, estimating process, team alignment, estimation design, expected accuracy, review and acceptance of estimate and idiosyncratic factors that are beyond the control of the project

team. Enshassi *et al.* (2007b) in analysing the effects of factors affecting cost estimating from the perspectives of contractors in Palestine revealed that the main factors are: location of the project, segmentation of the Gaza strip and limitations of movement between areas, political situation and closure of the Gaza strip. Odusami and Onukwube (2008) in their study of factors affecting the accuracy of pre-tender estimate focussed on the estimates of quantity surveyors. Seven most influential factors were identified from the study as; expertise of consultants, quality of information and flow requirements, project team experience, tender period and market condition, extent of completion of pre-contract design, complexity of design and construction and availability of labour and materials. They concluded that taking into consideration these factors at the inception of the project could improve the accuracy of preliminary cost advice consultant Quantity Surveyors give their clients. Al-Hasan *et al.* (2008) in a study to investigate current cost estimating practice of specialist trade contractors identified insufficient time for estimating, inadequate specifications, incomplete drawings, quality of project management, lack of historical cost data as the major factors affecting accuracy of estimating process in the United Kingdom. This study is aimed at identifying and assessing the effects of the most essential controllable factors affecting the accuracy of cost estimates from the perception of construction professionals with the view to evaluating the degree of importance of these factors in cost estimation of construction projects in Nigeria for improved cost performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

The population for the survey included construction professionals in the offices of clients, consultants, and contractors that are involved in bid preparation and contract execution in the six states of the North Eastern Geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Structured questionnaires were used to obtain information from the respondents in respect of the influencing factors drawn from literature. A total of 300 questionnaires was designed and sent to the offices of the respondents (100 for each category of respondents). 85, 82 and 76 number of questionnaires were successfully filled and returned from the offices of clients, consultants and contractors. In general, a total of 243 questionnaires were returned and analysed. This response can be seen as good because 84% of the total required was returned.

The first section of the questionnaire contained the background information of the respondents in respect of their academic qualification, work experience and type of organisation they work for in order to assist the researcher in ascertaining the reliability of the information provided. The second part of the questionnaire provided the respondent the opportunity of scoring the different factors based on a likert scale. The five level of scoring on the scale were extremely important (5 points), highly important (4 points), averagely important (3 points), somewhat important (2 points) and little importance (1 point).

Relative Importance index (RII) of each factor was calculated to determine the relative importance of the factor. The statistical relation in equation (1) was used for calculating the importance index (Shash and Ibrahim, 2005).

$$RII = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 a_i x_i}{5 \sum_{i=1}^5 x_i} \right) * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where a_i = constant expressing the weight given to i ; x_i = variable expressing the frequency of the response for I , $i = 1,2,3,4,5$ and illustrated as follows:

- x_1 = frequency of the "little importance" response and corresponding to $a_1=1$;
- x_2 = frequency of "somewhat importance" response and corresponding to $a_2=2$
- x_3 = frequency of "average importance" response and corresponding to $a_3 = 3$;
- x_4 = frequency of "high importance" response and corresponding to $a_4=4$;
- x_5 = frequency of "extreme importance" response and corresponding to $a_5= 5$;

The average index for each major criterion is the average of all the indices of the individual criteria within the category.

The importance indices were grouped to reflect the respondents' ratings as follows: Extremely important: $70 < I \leq 100$; highly important: $60 < I \leq 70$; averagely important: $50 < I \leq 60$; somewhat important: $40 < I \leq 50$; and little important: $0 < I \leq 40$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic profiles of the respondents showed that majority (56%) of the respondents have over 10 years of working experience i.e. 11% plus 41% (Fig. 1).

Majority (65%) possess a high level of academic qualification, i.e. Master Degree holders 13%, First Degree holders or H.N.D. holders 52%. The result is presented in Fig. 2.

The result in Fig. 3 further revealed that 34% of the respondents work as consultants, 35% work in the clients' organisation and 31% work in the contractors' organisation. Majority (68.5%) cover a wide spectrum of high ranking personnel in which more than half (50.1%) belong to the Top management level, such as director, deputy director and principals. Therefore the information provided by the respondents can be considered as reliable.

1. Effects of Input Control Factors On Cost Estimation

Input control factors regulate the input into the transformation process. This may be achieved through mechanisms such as selecting the right people, improving data quality and integrating design with cost estimation (Liu and Zhu, 2007). The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of Input Control Factors on Estimating

S/No	Factor	Importance index	Rank
1.	Project scope definition	75.30	1
2.	Historical data for similar contract.	71.93	2
3	Owners requirement clarity	70.53	4
4	Quality of the Cost data	71.34	3
5	Experience in Similar Contract	70.26	6
6	Experience in similar project	69.05	8
7	Completeness of design	70.39	5
8	Experience in local Market	69.45	7

The Result revealed that the input factor 'project scope definition' was indicated as the most influential factor within the group with relative importance index of 75.30 and is ranked first. Project scope definition is very necessary for cost planning and cost control activities. If the scope of the work is not definition helps in the appropriate budget allocation decision leading to significant cost performance. This factor is also considered a very important factor affecting cost estimating by Liu and Zhu (2007) and Ganiyu and Zubairu (2010). The second most influential factor from the perception of the professionals is the historical data of similar jobs with RII of 71.93. This is also in consonance with the findings of An *et al.* (2011) whose study also revealed that the availability of historical data is an important factor in producing effective estimates. The third most influential factor in the group is owner's requirement clarity with RII of 70.53 which was ranked third.

2. Effect of Behaviour Control Factors on Estimation

Behaviour control seeks to secure a specified type of behaviour in the belief that the behaviour delivers right results (Liu and Zhu, 2007). Behaviour controls are procedures that lay down a sequence of operations that must be followed. The influence of the various behaviour control factors is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of Behaviour Control Factors on Estimating

S/No	Factor	Importance index	Rank
1	Cost planning	74.97	3
2	Cost control activity	68.87	7
3.	Effective communication	74.07	4
4.	Estimators experience	77.69	1
5.	Adequacy of resources for cost estimating	71.23	6
6.	Experience of project manager	68.67	8
7.	Estimating Methodology	73.38	5
8.	Level of team integration	75.22	2

The result of the behaviour control factor indicates that, experience of the estimator was ranked first with a relative importance index of 77.69. The experience of the estimator enables the estimator to make appropriate decisions. This is followed by team integration and alignment with importance index of 75.22. Construction generally is a team work therefore if there is proper understanding and integration of the project team then reasonable estimates would be produced. Respondents indicated cost planning activity as the third most influential behaviour control factor relative with importance index of 74.97.

3. Effect of Output Control Factors on Estimation

The influence of the various output control factors is presented in Table 3. It showed that the factor expected accuracy of the estimates is the most important factor with relative importance index of 76.54 and is ranked first.

Table 3 Effect of Output Control Factors on Estimating

S/No	Factor	Importance index	Rank
1.	Expected accuracy	76.54	1
2.	Appraisal and acceptance of estimates	67.73	3
3.	Benchmarking	70.28	2

Output control specifies the schedule of outputs desired. The assumption is that, people who know what their targets are, adopt appropriate behaviour. The result of the effects of output control factors on cost estimation indicates that expected accuracy is the most influential factor with an importance index of 76.54. Accuracy level is one of the critical indicators of an effective estimate. An accurate estimate is essential to ensure that projects are allocated sufficient budget so that functional requirements are met (Pearce, 1997; Lowe *et al.*, 2006; Kim *et al.*, 2008a and Kim *et al.*, 2008b). Benchmarking is the second most influential factor based on the results. It is also an important factor because the procedure requires a standard against which the estimate is assessed. Appraisal and acceptance of estimates was ranked third respectively.

4. Overall Rank of all Factors

The overall ranking of factors in all the three groups is presented in Table 4. The ten most important factors are estimator's experience, expected accuracy, project scope definition, level of team integration, cost planning, effective communication, estimating methodology, historical data of similar contract, quality of the cost data and adequacy of resources for cost estimating with RII of 77.69, 76.54, 75.30, 75.22, 74.97, 74.07, 73.38, 71.93, 71.34 and 71.23 respectively.

Table 4 Effects of all Factors

S/No	Factor	RII	Rank
1	Estimators experience	77.69	1
2	Expected accuracy	76.54	2
3	Project scope definition	75.30	3
4	Level of team integration	75.22	4
5	Cost planning	74.97	5
6	Effective communication	74.07	6
7	Estimating Methodology	73.38	7
8	Historical data for similar contract.	71.93	8
9	Quality of the Cost data	71.34	9
10	Adequacy of resources for cost estimating	71.23	10
11	Owners requirement clarity	70.53	11
12	Completeness of design	70.39	12
13	Benchmarking	70.28	13
14	Experience in Similar Contract	70.26	14
15	Experience in local Market	69.45	15
16	Experience in similar project	69.05	16
17	Cost control activity	68.87	17
18	Experience of project manager	68.67	18
19	Appraisal and acceptance of estimates	67.73	19
20			20

CONCLUSION

Accurate cost estimates are essential to ensure that construction projects are allocated sufficient budgets so that all requirements are met. The accuracy of early stage estimates is affected by quite a number of factors. The control factors influencing cost estimates are categorized into input control factors, behaviour control factors

and output control factors. The results of the study revealed that project scope definition is an extremely important factor among the input factors group. Therefore projects scope must be defined at the early stage in order to have an effective estimate. Undefined projects would either be over-budgeted which affects its feasibility or under-budgeted which will certainly affect its profitability. Accurate prediction or forecasting of construction cost was also shown to be largely dependent on the availability and quality historical cost data, level of professional expertise, level of team integration, expected accuracy and cost planning activities among others.

The findings of this study is useful to both contractors and clients for them to be able to pay attention to these important factors for realizing effective estimates at the early or pre-tender stage. Further studies can be carried out to investigate the idiosyncratic factors in order to complement the research.

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